

Research on Lighting Protection of Heavy Helicopter

Shaodong ZHANG^{1,a}, Ting HU^{1,b}

¹Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics, China

^azsd011610112@nuaa.edu.cn, ^bht_01@nuaa.edu.cn,

Keywords: Heavy Helicopter, Composite Materials, Lighting Protection, TLM

1. ABSTRACT

In order to reduce the weight of heavy helicopters, composite materials are widely used. The structural weight mainly includes rotor weight, fuselage weight and landing gear weight. The structural weight coefficient is the percentage of the structural weight to the total weight of the helicopter. On the premise of meeting the structural strength of the body, its structural weight coefficient can be reduced to less than 30%. However, the introduction of composite materials into the helicopter body structure brings the special problem of lightning hazard.

Lightning strike has direct and indirect impact on helicopter. The direct impact of lightning stroke mainly includes the following two aspects. One is that the communication antenna exposed outside the fuselage is often damaged by lightning, resulting in communication system failure. On the other hand, the electrical conductivity of composites is poor, so it is difficult to conduct the current in a short time when lightning strikes. When the temperature rises sharply, the composites are deeply stratified or severely ablated, resulting in structural damage.

In terms of indirect impact, the high voltage and strong current generated by lightning strike will cause damage to helicopter systems, magnetization of individual helicopter components and interference to electronic equipment. Under low protection or no protection device, it may cause permanent damage to the helicopter and affect the normal operation of the system. Even worse, it may cause disastrous consequences.

The lightning strike accident of Mi-26, the biggest heavy helicopter in the world, was studied in the article. The direct effect of the attack was that the trailing edge of tail rotor and glass reinforced plastic pipe girder were detached by the sheering force and centrifugal force, which made the hammer brace unbalanced with a physical tearing of about 1m as the secondary damage. In order to investigate the cause of lightning stroke accident of Mi-26 helicopter, the 3D model of Mi-26 helicopter is established. The TLM (transmission line matrix method) of MS studio of CST is used to simulate and analyze the surface current distribution and internal electric field distribution when a specific lightning stroke path hits the tail rotor of Mi-26 helicopter. The analysis shows that when lightning strikes the composite structure, it leads to structural failure or large-area damage. Based on the guidance and standards of DOT / FAA / CT-89 / 22 and the interim defense standard 59-113 of the British MoD, several improvement measures are given. Typical lightning protection included adding wire and wire netting to the structure's surface which has possibility of direct lightning adherence.

2. INTRODUCTION

The Mi-26 is a multi-purpose heavy helicopter developed by the Mil Moscow Helicopter Plant (formerly Mil Design Bureau) of the former Soviet Union. It is the heaviest helicopter in the world today. The Mi-26 helicopter has an empty weight of 28,200 kg, a maximum payload of 20,00 kg, a normal take-off weight of 49,600 kg and a maximum take-off weight of 56,000 kg. The main structure of the Mi-26 helicopter^[1] is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Main structure of Mi-26 helicopter

The Mi-26 helicopter has a wide range of applications. In 2008, 230 people were trapped in the Tangjiashan quake lake after an 8.0 magnitude earthquake hit Wenchuan, Sichuan province, China. A Mi-26 heavy transport helicopter supported by Russia not only took two sorties to evacuate the affected people to safety, but also lifted a heavy excavator of 13.2 tons to the dam body of Tangjiashan quake lake^[2], see Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Lifting excavator

In 2013, a Mi-26 helicopter lifted a Tupolev TU 134 airliner from Pulkovo Airport to the Russian Emergencies Ministry's training centre based in a St Petersburg suburb, Rybatskoye^[3], as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Lifting Tu-134

3. LIGHTNING ACCIDENT OF MI-26

On the afternoon of May 11, 2010, a Mi-26TC helicopter, which had been introduced for one year and had flown for about 200 hours, was flying from Qingdao to Changchun for forest protection. When the flight was at an altitude of 2100m and there were clouds above and below, the Chinese pilot heard a strong noise in his earphones. The noise continued after he turned off the onboard radio installation group and then heard a loud bang. The rear fuselage shook violently, and then the VHF(very high frequency)transceiver, CVR (cockpit voice recorder), FDR (flight data recorder) and radio altimeter transceiver in the tail cabin all fell. The Russian captain believed that the tail rotor was damaged by lightning. The pilot correctly selected a cornfield backed by a mountain and made an emergency landing. The alternate landing was successful and there were no casualties because the crop field absorbed a lot of energy. The scene of the accident^[4] is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. A piece of tail rotor back off

On the day of the accident, the helicopter flew into the cloud after appearing static electricity accumulation characteristics, and then immediately suffered lightning^[4]. The damage caused by lightning strike led to continuous vibration of the helicopter, the falling off of FDR in the cabin, the breaking of connecting cable、 VHF transceiver and other equipment damping frame. Strong lightning current discharged between No.6 rotor and No. 5 tail rotor. No.6 rotor maintained the basic aerodynamic profile. Due to the temperature rise, deformation and melting of the metal honeycomb after conducting super current, the connection strength of the front and rear sections of the tail rotor was weakened. Under the condition of high-speed rotation, only part of the honeycomb structure was retained at the root of No. 5 tail rotor, and the rest of the rear sections were basically

separated. The metal honeycomb on the section had a large amount of dark brown particles with serious burning and melting. See Fig.5 and Fig.6 for damage^[4].

Fig. 5. Aluminum honeycomb structures at tail rotor root

Fig. 6. Dark brown particles on the section of metal honeycomb

The skin at the root of the rotor was torn and fallen off, and there were black scorch marks at the connection between the wing rib and the rotor girder. This was the ashing of the composite blade surface (thermal effect) caused by lightning strikes^[5]. The leading edge of the tail inclined beam had a physical tear mark about 0.8m long in the up and down direction. The reason could be that the tail rotor lost a large mass of the rear segment and the helicopter lost dynamic balance. The damage is shown in Fig.7.

Fig. 7. Dynamic response to tail relationship cracks about 0.8 meters

4. SIMULATION ANALYSIS OF MI-26 LIGHTNING STRIKE

Overall test with the experimental approach can identify the potential problem from the perspective of whole system, which makes it a necessary approach to testify the lightning protection performance of products^[6]. Although the techniques of generating high voltage and large current are both very mature, the simulation of lightning parameters in laboratory environment is closely related to the dimension and resistance of the specimen. The numerical prediction of the EM effects produced by a lightning stroke to an aircraft has the advantage of higher flexibility and lower costs with respect to the experimental approach^[7]. Thus, numerical simulation can be used to analyse the cause of lightning stroke accident of Mi-26 helicopter. In recent years, with the continuous improvement of electromagnetic calculation methods and electromagnetic simulation software development technology, 3D electromagnetic simulation software such as FEKO of EMSS company in South Africa, CST and EMA3D in Germany have played an increasingly important role in electromagnetic accurate calculation of the whole machine and equipment. D. Lalonde et al^[8] used EMA3D software to simulate the full-scale lightning strike of the aircraft, which complies with the Airworthiness Clause 981. The research on the indirect effect of aircraft lightning strike in China mainly focuses on the division of aircraft lightning strike attachment point and lightning strike attachment area. For example, Wen Hao and others^[9-11] used different numerical simulation software to conduct experimental research on lightning strike attachment point of reduced or equal scale model of aircraft, and divided the lightning strike attachment area of aircraft.

In this paper, the TLM of MS Studio of CST is used for numerical simulation analysis of the Mi-26 helicopter. According to the requirements of SAE ARP 5416A aircraft lightning test method, lightning current component A was used to simulate the lightning strike environment, and a 3D model of Mi-26 helicopter was established to analyse the surface current distribution and internal electric field distribution when a specific lightning strike path hit the tail rotor of the helicopter.

4.1 3D modeling of the Mi-26 helicopter

The model of Mi-26 helicopter in CST is shown in Fig.8. The length of the helicopter is 40.025 m, the height is 8.145 m, the rotor diameter is 32 m, and the rotor disc area is about 804.25m².

Fig. 8. The whole model of Mi-26 helicopter established in CST

The rotor, tail and other structures of the helicopter have small effect on the lightning transient electromagnetic effect. Therefore, on the premise of considering the computer

memory and simulation time, it is not necessary to take the structures such as rotor and tail into account, and the solid model is simplified by the hollowing operation. The simplified model is shown in Fig.9.

Fig. 9. The simplified model of Mi-26 helicopter established in CST

The fuselage is set as aluminum skin material, which has a relative dielectric constant of 9.4, a relative permeability of 1, a conductivity of 3.54×10^7 Siemens/m and a thickness of 158 mm.

4.2 Incentive source setting

In this article, the lightning strike path is set as entering the head of the fuselage and exiting from the tail, as shown in the solid orange line in Fig.9. The US military standard MIL-STD-464A measures and classifies lightning strikes. China's national military standard GJB1389 lightning strike standard also refers to the description of the US military standard. Equation (1) is the lightning strike current $I(t)$.

$$I(t) = 218.81[e^{-11.354t} - e^{-647.265t}](KA) \quad (1)$$

The transient waveform of lightning strike current is shown in Fig.10. And Fig.11 shows the transient waveform of lightning strike voltage.

Fig. 10. Transient waveform of lightning strike current

Fig. 11. Transient waveform of lightning strike voltage

4.3 The simulation results

Five probes were set at different positions as showed in Fig.9 to observe the electric and magnetic field intensity within 0-100 μ s respectively. The simulation results are shown in Fig.12 and Table 1.

(a) Point 1

(b) Point 2

(c) Point 3

(d) Point 4

(e) Point 5

Fig. 12. Intensity of magnetic field and electric field

Table 1. Electromagnetic effects at different probe positions

T=100 μ s	The number of probe				
	1	2	3	4	5
Maximum electric field intensity (V/m)	85	4,500	258	24,500	20,000
Maximum magnetic field intensity (A/m)	0.44	6.5	1.15	31	10
Maximum surface current density (A/m)	0.44	6.5	1.15	31	10

Fig. 13 shows the current distribution of Mi-26 helicopter at different times.

(a) T=0 μ s

(b) T= 749.051 ns

(c) T= 966.517 ns

Fig. 13. Current distribution of Mi-26 helicopter

4.4 The conclusion

By comparing the electromagnetic effects of different probes and observing the current distribution diagram of Mi-26 helicopter at different times, the following conclusions were drawn: the lightning current forms a current path through the deicing system of the main rotor and tail rotor among No.6 rotor, main reducer, fuselage, tail reducer and No. 5 tail rotor. Both ends of the current flow in and out are at No. 6 rotor and No. 5 tail rotor respectively. The strong lightning current causes instantaneous destructive damage to No. 5 tail rotor.

5. SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

Lightning accidents rarely occur in traditional metal-structured aircraft, because the metal body itself has a "Faraday cage" effect, which naturally shields high-voltage electromagnetic fields. The fourth-generation helicopters developed since the 1980s have used a large number of composite materials, which has accounted for 35 percent to 50 percent of the structural mass. In recent years, all-composite helicopters have also appeared. The composite material has high anti-fatigue and anti-corrosion properties, and the weight coefficient of the structure can be reduced to less than 30% under the premise of meeting the structural strength of the body. However, the introduction of composite materials into the structure of the helicopter's airframe presents a particular problem with the risk of lightning strikes. Due to the poor electrical conductivity of the composite material, when the composite material part is struck by lightning, it is difficult to conduct the current away in a short time, resulting in a rise in temperature. If the temperature is too high, the composite material will be deeply delaminated or severely ablated, resulting in structural damage. Therefore, the composite structure aircraft needs lightning protection design.

Guidance on the design of aircraft lightning protection can be found in the FAA Technical Report "Aircraft Lightning Protection Manual" (DOT/FAA/CT-89/22). Typical lightning protection includes the addition of wire or metal mesh where direct lightning attachment is likely to occur on the outer surface of composite structures. The effectiveness of lightning protection for composite structures should be verified by tests.

The Mi-26 tail rotor is an aluminium honeycomb structure. Lightning Protection Requirements for Aircraft in Service of the British MoD interim defence standard 59-113 states that aluminium honeycomb structures should not be used under the dielectric of the CFC if there is any risk of lightning current flowing within the structure^[12].

Based on the above guidance and standards, the following improvement measures are given:

5.1 Electric bonding

Electric bonding means connected aircraft equipment case and structure by braided strap or jumper in order to obtain same electric potential.

The initial attachment point or lightning sweep attachment point when the aircraft is struck by lightning is the entry point of lightning charge. They usually locate in front of the tail of the aircraft. The exit point of lightning stroke is the discharge point of the aircraft to the atmosphere during lightning strike. They are usually located at the tail of the aircraft, possibly on the flat tail, vertical tail, the trailing edge of the rudder or the tail tip of the fuselage. Because the rudder surfaces such as flat tail and rudder have transmission pairs that need lubrication, it is difficult to form a conductive path between the body and the rudder surface. After composite materials are adopted on aircraft, because electric properties are different between composite materials and metals so that bonding resistance that is specified in GJB358—87 cannot apply partly. Better electric bonding design is needed^[13].

When the lightning arc cannot be attached to helicopters and there are enough bonding wires to transmit lightning current, the cross-sectional area of a single copper wire shall not be less than $20mm^2$. If aluminum wire is used, the impact current carrying capacity of its section shall be equivalent to that of copper wire, and the electric bonding wire and its joint are not allowed to be connected by welding^[14].

In 1995, a Super Puma AS332L helicopter was struck by lightning in the North Sea. In this paper, the electric bonding is improved with reference to AS332L helicopter blade. The improved blade still has glass fiber on the leading edge, but under the protective cover there is bonding iron between the grounding bolt and the hub, as shown in Fig.14.

Fig. 14. Original and modified tail rotor blades of AS332L

5.2 Grid protection method

For composite structure aircraft, one of the most effective lightning protection measures is to lay precision metal mesh plate. The metal wire can be woven into cloth or knitwear by standard textile process. Aluminum wire mesh is the best in terms of weight, cost and efficiency. Aluminum wire mesh has the characteristics of the lightning protection layer system^[15]:

- It is not only the lightest for the lightning protection of the given specification, but also the least damage in the simulated lightning discharge test.

- It has the ability to withstand multiple lightning strikes and transmit a high amount of charge at the same time.
- Aluminum wire mesh can be easily made into complex curved surface, and can simply use composite matrix as adhesive and parts for one-time curing.

Therefore, it is a high-quality and efficient lightning protection layer [15]. Some advanced metal wire mesh are shown in Fig.15 and Fig.16.

Fig. 15. Thin film mesh plate made of different metals

Fig. 16. Aluminum film produced by Dexmet

5.3 Surface layer protection method

Conductive paint is composed of resin or rubber as well as conductive filler and solvent. It mainly relies on conductive filler particles dispersed in the polymer to form a continuous network chain and discharge charge. Radome normally conduct electricity by applying conductive paint (BMS10-21) and installing lightning strips. Electrostatic current is carried through fasteners to the metal structure of the fuselage.

Integument Technologies of New York developed a decorative layer that can be affixed and torn off after a structure is formed. It is lighter than the traditional mesh material, which can not only replace the surface painting of composite material, but also have the conductive effect of electrostatic eliminator. After lightning strikes, the bonded epoxy adhesive vaporizes and can be replaced quickly [16].

Sikorsky plans to use the high conductivity epoxy film or coating developed by Lord crop as the lightning protection material for S-97 "Raider" helicopter. LORD UltraConductive™ spray coatings and films are filled polymeric materials that behave like metals in their ability to conduct electricity and heat, but can be applied as a paint, or by draping as an adhesive film onto composite surfaces for lightning strike protection. Its weight is only half that of the traditional expanded copper foil surfacing film, and the surface finish is also greatly improved. It can not only provide the same lightning protection for the composite materials, but also improve the product quality and production capacity [17].

6. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

After the Mi-26 helicopter accident, although the helicopter company has taken measures to replace all five tail rotors, the Mi-26 designed in the 1980s is not resistant to lightning, which is a design defect and can not meet the current standard. Through the analysis of the accident and model simulation research, some improvement measures with reference value are put forward, which provides more reliable modification suggestions for the design and research of helicopters in China.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Rotary-winged hero", *Modeler-Constructor*, no.8,1989.
- [2] Yiping Lin, Meng Wei, "Disaster relief 'Hercules' Mi-26", *Aerospace Knowledge*, no.9,2008, pp. 56-59.
- [3] NIKOLAI LITOVKIN "Heavy lifting: Giant helicopter MI-26 gets upgrade", *Science & Tech*, no.8,1989.
- [4] Ting HU, Hong YAN, Xiaochun WANG, "Helicopters Lightning Protection", *Journal of Guilin University of Technology*, no.4,2013, pp. 775-778.
- [5] Lei Ma, "Lightning Damage of Wind Turbine Blade and Its Protective Measures", *Science & Technology Information*, vol.20, no.1,2022, pp. 51-54.
- [6] Chunlei WANG, Lihua SHI, Yantao DUAN, Shangchen FU, Liyuan SU, "An Overview of Overall Lightning Testing System Abroad", *Environmental Technology*, vol.37, no.6,2019, pp. 185-189.
- [7] MAURIZIO A, MARCELLO D, "Lightning indirect effects certification of a transport aircraft by numerical simulation", *IEEE Trans on Electro-magnetic Compatibility*, vol.50, no.3,2008, pp. 513-523.
- [8] Lemaire D, Garrido F, Peres G. et al, "A unified approach for lightning and low frequencies HIRF transfer functions measurements on A380", *International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, 2009.
- [9] Hao WEN, Xinyu HOU, Hong WANG, "Research on Lightning Attachment Points Test on Airplane Model", *High Voltage Engineering*, vol.32, no.7,2006, pp. 90-92.
- [10] Yulong ZHAO, Guangbin LIU, Zhiyong YU, "Research on Lightning Attachment Points Simulation for Aircraft", *Journal of Microwaves*, vol.28, no.4,2012, pp. 39-42.
- [11] Cheng GAO, Shuang SONG, Yongchao GUO, et al, "Study of numerical simulation of aircraft attachment points and lightning zoning", *Chinese Journal of Radio Science*, vol.27, no.6,2012, pp. 1238-1243,1267.
- [12] MOD interim defence standard 59-113, "Lightning protection requirements for aircraft in service", 1995
- [13] Tianshun WANG, "Analysis on electric bonding for composite materials", *Aircraft Design*, no.3,2001, pp. 55-60.
- [14] GJB 358-1987, "Electrical bonding requirements for military aircraft", 1987.
- [15] Chaohui Ji, Qianqian MA, Zhiping WANG, et al, "Design and Application of Lightning Protection Layer of Airplane Composite Materials", *Aerospace Materials & Technology*, vol.41, no.5,2011, pp. 50-54.
- [16] Zhien WU, "Protection Against Lightning of Aircraft Composite Components", *Aeronautical Manufacturing Technology*, no.15,2011, pp. 96-99.
- [17] Durso S.R, Sanquer E. "Application Versatility Of Conductive Polymer Coatings As Lightning Strike Protection" *ICOLSE 2015*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

All of the authors deserve significant recognition for their contributions and input to this effort.